

Short Review

Waste water treatment process of paper mill, pulp recovery and recycling techniques

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Abstract: Paper sector in Bangladesh is currently expanding day-by-day to meet the increasing demand of industrial, writing/printing and specialty papers. Paper mills have adverse effects on the environment by producing huge quantity of wastewater. Yearly, approximately 14 million m³ wastewater is being discharged to the surface water bodies and irrigated lands without no/limited treatment. Wastewater treatment is a process used to remove contaminants from wastewater or sewage and convert it into an effluent that can be returned to the water cycle with acceptable impact on the environment, or reused for various purposes (called water reclamation). Four common ways to treat wastewater include physical water treatment, biological water treatment, chemical treatment, and sludge treatment.

Keywords: Bangladesh, paper mill, surface water, water treatment.

Introduction

Waste water is treated in 3 phases: 1. Primary (solid removal), 2. Secondary (bacterial decomposition), and 3. Tertiary (extra filtration).

Primary treatment removes material that will either float or readily settle out by gravity. The shredded material is removed later by sedimentation or flotation processes. ... Primary and secondary treatment of sewage, using the activated sludge process

Stages of water treatment are.

(1) Collection ; (2) Screening and Straining ; (3) Chemical Addition ; (4) Coagulation and Flocculation ; (5) Sedimentation and Clarification ; (6) Filtration ; (7) Disinfection ; (8) Storage ; (9) and finally Distribution.

There are four ways in which a water treatment plant can operate: Effluent Treatment, Sewage Treatment, Common and Combined Effluent Treatments, and Activated Sludge Treatment.

The major aim of wastewater treatment is to remove as much of the suspended solids as possible before the remaining water, called effluent, is discharged back to the environment. As solid material decays, it uses up oxygen, which is needed by the plants and animals living in the water

There are two basic stages in the treatment of wastes, primary and secondary, which are outlined here. In the primary stage, solids are allowed to settle and removed from wastewater. The secondary stage uses biological processes to further purify wastewater. Sometimes, these stages are combined into one operation.

Table 3: Typical wastewater characteristics from a mill using imported pulp/wastepaper as raw material

Parameter	Unit	Wastewater characteristics
pH	-	6.9-8.7
Suspended Solids	mg/L	412-1181
Dissolved Solids	mg/L	106-715
BOD ₅ at 20°	mg/L	90-150
COD	mg/L	320-810

Table 4: Influent and effluent characteristics for a local paper mill producing tissue, printing, offset, cigarette paper etc

Parameter	Influent(untreated)	Effluent (treated)
Average flow rate	200 m ³ /hr	
pH	7.37	7.15
TDS	450 mg/L	415 mg/L
TSS	470 mg/L	41 mg/L
BOD ₅	110 mg/L	12 mg/L
COD	225 mg/L	35 mg/L
Color	turbid/white	Colorless

Water pollution from pulp and paper mills can be minimized through proper effluent characterization and design of appropriate treatment facilities. In this article different techniques of wastewater treatment for paper mills are discussed. Case study based on treatability analysis and jar test for a paper mill producing 200 m³/h of effluent is provided. On the basis of the case study a simplified treatment process is proposed. Proper treatment of such mills would not only save our environment but can also be beneficial for the industries by water usage minimization.

MAIN PULPING PROCESS

Sulfate or Kraft pulping is the main pulping process was invented in Germany in 1884 and remains the dominating technology today. Usually known as "kraft pulping" which relies on a combination of heat, chemicals and mechanical pulping to convert the wood into a smooth, soft pulp suitable for use in paper making.

The Kraft pulping process has three main functions:

- Minimizing the environmental impact of waste material (black liquor) from the pulping process.
- Recycling pulping chemicals, NaOH and Na₂S;
- Co-generating steam and power

Gasification

Advantages for Chemical Recovery Process:

- It can be used with virtually all wood species.
- It can easily handle the extractives in most coniferous wood
- The pulp has very good strength.
- The recovery process for the chemicals is well established.
- More effective at removing impurities like resins.

This traditional Kraft Pulping has undergone many changes since 1884, and its till have many opportunities in future. Some the recent trends are:

Developments in the chemical recovery process, has introduced black liquor gasification which proves to be a potential replacement for recovery boilers. Black liquid gasifiers with this capability are still in the development stage and fullscale implementation is still a futuristic approach.

Borate Auto causticizing

The process involves adding sodium borate into the liquor system so that it forms tri-sodium borate (Na_3BO_3) in the recovery boiler smelt. This technology has the potential for completely eliminating the causticizing plant and the lime kiln, making the kraft process much simpler.

Recycling includes the three steps below, which create a continuous loop, represented by the familiar recycling symbol.

- Step 1: Collection and Processing. ...
- Step 2: Manufacturing. ...
- Step 3: Purchasing New Products Made from Recycled Materials

There is currently growing interest in the MBR (membrane bioreactor) process in municipal and industrial wastewater treatment. MBR is used in the paper industry as end-of-pipe technology as well as process integrated measure for the reduction of the concentration of detrimental substances in the water circuit. Especially in terms of effluent quality and economical aspects a MBR is a sustainable technology for the industrial wastewater treatment.

3FM technology

The purpose of water filtration is to remove particles and colloids which either disturb the industrial process, deteriorate the quality of the final product or support bacteria and viruses that are a danger for human health.

The 3FM system (Flexible Fibre Filter Module) is a new high speed filtration device that can be substituted for conventional solid-liquid separation process such as coagulation, settling and sand filtration. Ultimately, the solutions to the profound challenge ahead – the shifting of industry awareness and the transformation of the industry’s lifeblood – requires continuous research and technology to be developed in the years to come.

Materials and methods

The production of chemical pulp in recent times is 180 million tons per year; while the production of eucalyptus pulp has increased intensively, especially in the southern hemisphere. The pulp and paper industry has long been considered a large consumer of natural resources (wood and water) and one of the largest sources of pollution to the environment (air, water courses and soil).

Important efforts are being made to reduce the pollutant levels and water consumption of the industry. The wastewater composition, and therefore, the efficiency of effluent treatments and characteristics of the discharges to water are strongly dependent on the applied technology and raw materials. Despite a large body of literature on softwood-based wastewater, few studies have examined the characteristics of kraft eucalyptus bleaching effluents and their behaviour in the different biological treatments. The largest secondary treatment systems today use the activated sludge process. Sixty to seventy-five per cent of all the biological effluent treatment plants within the pulp and paper industry use this kind of treatment system

Effluent standards for pulp and paper mills as per ECR 1997

Parameter	Large plants	Small plants
Production capacity	>50 tonnes/day	<50 tonnes/day
pH	6-9	6-9
Suspended Solids (mg/L)	100	100
BOD ₅ at 20°C (mg/L)	30	50
COD (mg/L)	300	400
Wastewater flow	200	200 (from agricultural raw materials)
m ³ /tonne paper		75 (from wastepaper)

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The process of waste paper recycling most often involves mixing used/old paper with water and chemicals to break it down. It is then chopped up and heated, which breaks it down further into strands of cellulose, a type of organic plant material; this resulting mixture is called pulp, or slurry

Tear the paper into small pieces and put into a blender with warm water. Blend until the mixture becomes a fairly smooth pulp. 2. Assemble your “mold”; attach your screen to your frame using duck tape, staples, or any other method that will keep the screen affixed to the frame's edges.

Conclusion

With today’s increasingly high energy and chemical costs and stringent environmental regulations, the need for improved recovery of chemicals from the pulp and paper making process has become a critical economic factor in the industry. It is essential that mills maximize steam and power production capacity, reduce recirculating chemical dead loads, and minimize chemical losses.

How paper made

Paper is an essential outcome from the forest industry, used in various forms and shapes. This different forms of paper is made by pulping of the wood, bleaching the pulped wood, spreading these bleached pulp into sheets ultimately converting it to paper. With different stages of designing

the paper, various chemicals are used to give the paper its present properties, such as the bleaching chemicals that make paper white

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Conflicts of Interest

No.

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